

CONSUMER BEHAVIOR AND FACTORS INFLUENCING PURCHASE DECISION OF DURABLE GOODS

Dr. K. Veerakumar

Assistant Professor in Commerce - BPS, NGM College (Autonomous),
Pollachi, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. K. Veerakumar, "Consumer Behavior and Factors Influencing Purchase Decision of Durable Goods", International Journal of Computational Research and Development, Volume 2, Issue 2, Page Number 7-10, 2017.

Abstract:

The Consumer behavior or buyer behavior has gained increased importance in a consumer oriented marketing planning and management. The study of consumer behavior is an attempt to understand what the consumer want, why they want. Consumer behavior reflects the totality of consumer's decisions with respect to acquisition, consumption and disposition of goods, services, time and idea by human decision making. It also includes whether, why, when, where, how, how much and how often and how long consumer will use or dispose of an offering.

Key Words: Consumer, Behaviour & Durable Goods

1. Introduction:

The buying behavior of consumer has become a great necessity in modern marketing system, because success or failure ultimately depends upon the buying behavior of the target customers considered individually or a group. Therefore in order to undertake the marketing programmes among different segment markets, the marketing management must find out the various factors that influences in buying decisions of the consumer. The character, behavior and attitude of consumer are the important dimensions in the decision making process. The subject of buying behavior is relatively a new discipline of the study of marketing. It has now become the central topic of modern marketing since the ultimate aim of marketing is consumer satisfaction and profit making. Consumer behavior can be defined as "the decision-making process and physical activity involved in acquiring, evaluating, using and disposing of goods and services". According to Webster, "Buying behavior is all psychological, social and physical behavior of potential customer as they become aware of evaluate purchase consume and tell other people about the product and services. In other words of Walter and Paul, "consumer behavior is the process whereby individual decide what, when, how and from where to purchase goods and service". Thus the buyer behavior may be defined as that behavior exhibited by people in planning, purchasing and using economic goods and service in the satisfaction of their wants.

2. Characteristics of Buyer Behaviour:

- ✓ Buyer behaviour comprise mental and physical activates of a buyer when he wants to buy goods and service to satisfy his needs.
- ✓ It includes both visible and invisible of buyer. The visible activates refer to physical activity like actually going to the market place, buying the product and consuming them. The invisible activates on the other hand, refer to mental activates like thinking about the product, deciding to buy or not to buy that product, to buy one brand instead of another etc.
- ✓ Buyer behaviour is very complex and dynamic also. It is constantly changing requiring certain adjustment. The marketing management which fails to make such adjustments, would certainly lose its market.
- ✓ An individual buying behaviour is also influenced by internal factors such as needs, habits, instincts, motives, attitudes etc and also by outside or environmental factors such as family, social, groups, culture, status, positions, economic and business conditions. In narrow sense, consumer behaviour is the act of a consumer when he is engaged in buying and consuming a good or a service.

Consumer durables involve any type of product purchased by consumers that is manufactured for long-term use and includes durable goods like TV, Washing Machine, Refrigerator, Mixie, Grinder, Laptop/PC, Mobile Phones, Water Purifier, Microwave Oven, Air conditioner. In the competitive market, the prospective buyer is prepared to choose the right brand based on their needs. All the purchases made by a consumer involves a certain decision making process.

3. Statement of the Problem:

An understanding of purchase behavior of consumers towards durable goods is essential as it reflects the influence of brands, price, quality, quantity, mode of purchase, etc. The success of the market or the failure depends on the purchase behavior of consumers. Consumer is nerve centre of the modern marketing, understanding his behavior is quite essential for efficient and effective marketing management. Customers may state their needs, wants but act otherwise. They may not be in touch with their deeper motivations. India's consumer market is riding the crest of the country's economic boom. Driven by a young population with access to disposable incomes and easy finance options, the consumer market has been throwing up staggering figures.

Marketing problems confronted from the consumers' behavior has a greater degree of similarity with behavioral problems.

4. Review of Literature:

Venkateswara and Reddy studied about the marketing of television sets among 300 households of Prakasam district of Andhra Pradesh. It was found that, in most of the cases head of a household and his wife acted as a decision maker. Influence of wealth, income, education and savings were found negative. But influence of advertisement was found higher (97%) in the study.

Losarwar attempted to examine the influence of socio-economic profile, role of family and reference groups, life style, brand awareness, factors influencing, buying motives, effectiveness of promotional plans on the purchase decision in respect of select five durable products - Television, Washing Machine, Refrigerator, Mixer and Fan. The results of the study revealed that majority of the consumers purchased the television, washing machine and Refrigerator from authorized dealers whereas mixer and fan from retailers. Company's advertisements, reputation, price and quality of the product were some of the factors that influenced the choice of consumer durables. The study concluded that the modern market is highly competitive and transitional. Thus, the role played by consumer is very prominent and the marketer should consider the behavior and attitude of the consumers before introducing the product into the market.

Hitesh D. Vyas explored the important factors and sources of information in purchase of consumer durables among households in Bhavnagar city. He opined that the market for consumer durables has become more competitive and the producers of durable products should understand consumers' interest much to find higher sale of their products. His study analysed the important factors and sources of information that influence the purchase of durable goods. The study revealed that company or brand name, guarantee/warranty, price and after sales service were the important factors in purchase of durables. The sources of important information were authorized dealers' shop, technical expert advice, role of TV as media and influence of friends, relatives and neighbors. The study concluded that the competitive market provides opportunity on one hand and threats on the other hand to both the consumer and the producer. Manufacturers or marketers have improved core products with value addition to enhance customer satisfaction more in the similar price range.

5. Objectives of the Study:

To identify for the above questions the researcher framed the following objectives are as follows:

- ✓ To study the socio-economic profile of the selected consumers.
- ✓ To identify the factors influencing for purchase decision.

6. Methodology:

The data for the purpose of the present study have been collected through primary and secondary data. Primary data has been collected through structured questionnaire. The sources of secondary data include published data such as data from books, journals, periodicals, brochures, reports, etc.

Area of the Study: The study was undertaken in Pollachi taluk.

Sample Size: A total of 50 respondents residing in the Pollachi city form the sample. Convenience sampling technique was followed for collecting response from the respondents.

Tools for Analysis: The statistical tools used for the purpose of this study are simple Percentages.

7. Profile of Selected Consumers:

In Pollachi taluk there are 50 consumers were taken for this study by adopting convenient sampling method. The demographic factors of selected consumers include variables such as age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, occupation, type of family, number of members and monthly income. It is presented in table 1.1.

Table 1.1: Personal Profile

Particulars	Numbers	Percentage
Age		
Up to 20 Years	25	50.00
20-30 Years	10	20.00
Above 30 Years	15	30.00
Gender		
Female	20	40.00
Male	30	60.00
Marital Status		
Married	20	40.00
Unmarried	30	60.00
Educational Qualification		
Up To School Level	10	20.00
Under Graduate	30	60.00
Diploma	10	20.00

Occupation		
Student	15	30.00
Employer	20	40.00
Business	15	30.00
Type of family		
Joint family	40 1	80.00
Nuclear family	10	20.00
Number of members		
Up to 3 members	10	20.00
3-6 members	25	50.00
6 and above	15	30.00
Monthly income (Rs.)		
Up to Rs.15000	10	20.00
Rs.15001 - Rs. 20000	25	50.00
Above Rs. 20000	15	30.00
Factors Influencing the Purchase Decision		
Price	5	10.00
Colour	7	14.00
Brand Preference	9	18.00
More time consumption	5	10.00
Offers / Discounts	6	12.00
Shape / Size	5	10.00
Brand Image	7	14.00
Model / Design	6	12.00

Table 5.2 clearly explain that majority of the respondents (50.00%) are belonging to the age group up to 20 years, most of the consumers (100.00 %) are male, majority of the consumers (60.00%) are unmarried, most of the consumers (60.00%) are under graduates. Majority of the women consumers (40.00%) are employed in both public and private sector, majority of the consumers (80.00%) are in joint family, most of the consumers (50.00%) family having 3-6 members and majority of the consumers (50.00%) monthly income between Rs.15001 – Rs.20000. Most of the consumers (18.00%) are feel that brand preference as the primary factor while purchasing their products.

8. Findings, Suggestions and Conclusion:

The various findings of the study are given in the following:

- ✓ Majority of the respondents (50.00%) are belonging to the age group up to 20 years,
- ✓ All the consumers (100.00 %) are female,
- ✓ Majority of the consumers (60.00%) are single,
- ✓ Most of the consumers (60.00%) are under graduates.
- ✓ Majority of the consumers (40.00%) are employed in both public and private sector.
- ✓ Majority of the consumers (80.00%) are in joint family.
- ✓ Most of the consumers (50.00%) family having 3-6 members and
- ✓ Majority of the consumers (50.00%) monthly income between Rs.15001 – Rs.20000.
- ✓ Most of the consumers (18.00%) are feel that brand preference as the primary factor while purchasing their products.

9. Suggestions of the Study:

- ✓ Demand for consumer durables is more volatile since it moves rapidly or evaporates quickly in relation to business conditions. Marketers separate the current demand for durable goods in terms of replacement old products and expansion of the total stock demand for such goods.
- ✓ Consumers prefer high valued consumer durables of well established brands. The marketers and manufacturers of the consumer durables must try to convert the brand consciousness into brand loyalty for their well established brands. The consumer behaviour in this direction should properly be exploited by the manufacturers and dealers to maximize their sales.
- ✓ The buyers of consumer durables have largely shown their preference to make extensive enquiry from the dealers of different brands of the products. This trait should be emulated by all the buyers in order to avoid post purchase dissatisfaction about the quality and performance of the products.
- ✓ Concessions in the price, price reductions, discounts sell, gifts, etc., have become common practices. The buyers of consumer durables should try to avail of these benefits, whenever they are available however, the buyers of such goods should not be lured mere by consciousness without considering the quality and performance aspects of these higher value products.

- ✓ The buyers of the consumer durables should insist that all the technical information are revealed on the use of durable products to enable them to use the products without any technical fault leading to frequent repairs, free servicing of the durables by dealers during the guarantee period insisted upon the buyers.

10. Conclusion:

The market for consumer durables is becoming more competitive now a days. Therefore, the producer of durable products should understand consumer interest much to find higher sale of their products. Marketers communicate with consumers and try to convince through every possible media. To achieve success in the market, it has become highly inevitable to produce goods as preferred by the customer, as he is the kingpin around whom the entire marketing activity revolves. Thus, a marketer who understands the behaviour of the consumers and plan his marketing strategies to suit the needs and aspirations of the target market will definitely have an advantage over his competitors.

11. References:

1. Venkateswara. M. and Reddy. B., "Marketing of TV sets – A Study of External and Internal Influence on Consumer Behaviour", Indian Journal of Marketing, Vol.27 (8): 20-24, August 1997.
2. Losarwar. S.G., "Consumer Behaviour towards Durable Products – A Study with reference to Marathwada Region", Indian Journal of Marketing, November 2002, pp.6-9.
3. Ruche Trehan and Harman Deep Singh, "A Comparative Study on Urban and rural Consumer Behaviour", Indian Journal of Marketing, Vol. XXXIII, No.8, August 2003, pp.7-11.
4. Mubarak Ali, K. "A study of the influence of family members and their interaction in the purchase decision (with special reference to durable goods)" – Ph.D Thesis, Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirapalli, February 2007.
5. Illias. K., "A Study on Consumer Behaviour towards Durable Products (with specific reference to TV Users in Thiruvananthapuram District, Kerala)", January 2008.
6. Dr. Hitesh D. Vyas, "Consumer Purchase of Consumer Durables: A Factorial Study", International Journal of Management & Strategy, July – December, 2010, Vol.1, No.1, pp. 1-8/13.
7. Dr. Sarwade. W.K., "Consumer Behaviour and Marketing Trends of Consumer Durables in Aurangabad District", Pacific Publication, New Delhi, 2011, pp. 240-259.
8. K. Veerakumar & A. Venkedasubramaniam (2016) article titled "A Study on Consumer Satisfaction Towards Selected Health Drinks In Pollachi Taluk" International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Vol-II, Issue-I, Feb – 2016. P.No.112-115.